

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMPETITIONS IN THE PROCESS OF SCHOOL PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract.

The article analyzes in detail the attitude of students to school sports events, the influence of schoolchildren's interest on the activities of pedagogues. The conducted research helps to understand the need to further develop and introduce various sports activities to the activities of general education schools and all sports organizations of the city.

Keywords.

health, students, general education schools, teacher, coach, athlete, motivation, interest, competitions, holiday events.

Enter. The quality of the population determines the future of the country. The state pays special attention to the physical and social health of the young generation. During the last decades, there has been a decrease in the level of attitude towards health and physical fitness of the population in our country. "Adolescents' health directly affects their future life, their ability to have a career, build a family and raise children. Children from the middle school age should exercise their bodies in a sustainable manner, adults to prepare for life, its rapid growth, personality and outlook of the person are rapidly forming," said our country's president Sh. Mirziyoyev. In such a period, children are especially vulnerable and sometimes protected from the difficulties and dangers of today's world, but it is very important to help children in this responsible time and pay great attention to their health in the first place." development is an important component. The social policy of the state, which reveals people's abilities, satisfies their interests in strengthening and improving their health, makes it possible to reach their potential, improve the quality of life, achieve good things, as well as improve their results in education and sports activities. causes it to go away.

The main goals of health care from childhood:

- strengthening and protection of children's health;
- improving the quality of medical care for children;

- creating favorable conditions for children's development.

The purpose of the study

One of the main tasks for teachers is to form healthy lifestyle skills and family health culture as the main value, including providing information to parents. To educate and shape the young generation on the basis of health development, it is to activate the activity of children in various areas of their life with physical education. In the organization of these processes, the organization and organization of physical education and sports competitions, due to the need to maintain the health of schoolchildren, health measures should be developed by the secondary school.

Research organization methods. Improving children's health, all competitions are included in the uniform calendar of sports events in the regional, district, city stages every year and approved by the head.

The participants of this organized school club are the basis for all planned activities, their tasks are: organization, selection of children, focus on the type of sports, work with parents, "Olympic Reserves" sports school", "children's and teenagers' sports school", "swimming pools" to establish close relations with the coaches of BOSM. Mutually beneficial meetings will be held with general education schools in their region regarding the activities of mutual health promotion. Involvement of schoolchildren in activities aimed at strengthening their health, increasing their interest, forming an active life position, which helped them to put sports and a healthy lifestyle at the beginning of their activities. it is conducted under the guidance of physical education teachers starting from elementary grades

Research: School physical education classes, sports clubs and sports clubs strengthen the character, education of qualities such as purposefulness, psychological endurance, stress resistance, team spirit and the will to win, world view and dedication increases. The questionnaire identified the main types of motivation to engage in physical activity. When conducting school sports events, the teacher sees the following: the sports potential of children will help to choose the most in the future. games Festivals Sports events Presidential competitions Touristic Spartakiad processions "Happy starts" a certain type of sport for the purpose of physical self-improvement and health. At each stage, he always carelessly emphasizes the positive role of physical exercise in strengthening health and physical development, gradually leading students to achieve high results. In the last stages, the teacher together with the coach needs to form a conscious attitude to the student's physical condition, to consciously define the feelings aimed at the goals of achieving high results in sports, which will allow the student to

develop sports ability. It helps to involve students in various competitions. As a result of the survey on the motivation of students, the main types of the meaning of competitions at each age were determined, activities that help to realize the interests of each participant of the stage were selected for each stage. Findings made it possible to plan activities that will help to create interest among students and teachers. The most important factor for children of this age is the game approach to all activities. A characteristic feature of game events is emotionality. A positive tone is the most important condition for health, supports interest in physical exercises, allows you to provide the following standards without additional emotional stress. Children are interested and boredom disappears when there is work. Monotonous, monotonous activities kill any desire to do sports and various exercises and games, they take children away, sometimes they forget about time

Research results and discussion. In order to organize and hold events 2, 3, 4, the following conditions must be observed: 1. Develop a scenario, organize public awareness and attract students to everyone who wants to participate in the event;

2. Creating a solemn and festive atmosphere, combining sports activities and creative competitions in one event. 3. Observance of traditional opening and closing ceremonies, specific rules for each section of the celebration or competitions;

4. Impartial arbitration, in accordance with the Regulations, parties to attract judges (sports schools, children's art center, youth clubs of workers);

5. Awarding the winners and participants of the event, selecting the best participants for the presentation of the physical education asset of the school, cities in regional and federal events;

6. The duration of the competition should not exceed: for elementary school students: 1-1, 5 hours, for middle school students: 1.5-2.5 hours, for seniors: not more than 5 hours

Conclusion The organization and conduct of the sports holiday is based on the following principles: educational direction; mass recruitment students to participate in the celebration; students freely choose the type of lesson; appropriateness of competitive exercises and appropriateness of level fitness, gender and age of participants; safety of participants, judges and spectators; student initiatives to encourage activity and creativity; appearance and educational nature of the event. A teacher can instill a lasting love for physical education and sports, depending on how fit and healthy his skills are.

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